

THE TECHNOLOGY OF USING MODERN METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' ORAL SPEECH IN ENGLISH CLASSES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7734331>

ELSEVIER

Received: 14-03-2023
Accepted: 14-03-2023
Published: 22-03-2023

Axmedova Nargiza Bobir qizi

Is'hoqon Ibrat nomidagi Namangan davlat chet tillar instituti 1-bosqich magistranti

Abstract: In this author, the innovative methods and technologies of students' oral speech development in English language classes are used in practice through the "case study" method.

Keywords: innovative methods, case study, algorithm, group, process.

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ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ МЕТОДИК В РАЗВИТИИ УСТНОЙ РЕЧИ УЧАЩИХСЯ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Received: 14-03-2023
Accepted: 14-03-2023
Published: 22-03-2023

Abstract: В данной статье автор инновационные методы и технологии развития устной речи учащихся на занятиях по английскому языку применяются на практике посредством метода «кейс-стади».

Keywords: инновационные методы, тематическое исследование, алгоритм, группа, процесс.

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INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA O'QUVCHILAR OG'ZAKI NUTQINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA ZAMONAVIY METODLARDAN FOYDALANISH TEHNALOGIYASI

Received: 14-03-2023
Accepted: 14-03-2023
Published: 22-03-2023

Abstract: Ushbu maqolada muallif ingliz tili darslarida o'quvchilar og'zaki nutqini rivojlantirishning innovatsion uslub va tehnalogiyalaridan foydalanadi, hamda "case study" metodi orqali uni amaliyotda qo'llaydi.

Keywords: innovatsion metodlar, case study, algoritm, guruh, rivojlanish, jarayon

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Introduction The case study method is a method of active analysis of a problem situation based on learning by solving specific situational tasks. The essence of the case study method: students divided into groups should analyze the situation and work out a practical solution. The end of the process is the evaluation of the proposed algorithms and their discussion within the framework of a general discussion in the context of the problem. The case method was first used in the

educational process in 1870 at the Harvard Law School by the Dean of the Faculty of Law, Professor of Law Christopher Columbus Langdell. "Using Socratic method (question - answer), developing the method of trial and error, he invited students to work with primary sources (court cases, decisions of the Court of Appeal, etc.), and then draw their own conclusions, present their own interpretations and analysis. Langdell's approach differed sharply from traditional teaching (lectures, seminars) by inductive empiricism and was met with huge resistance" [1]. But, despite this, in the first three years, the method was established not only at Harvard. Its uniqueness and effectiveness were evaluated in six other legal institutions schools. Instead of traditional lectures, students considered and judged real legal situations that had occurred in life. Students prepared for classes in advance by studying folders with real documents in the form of audio and video formats. The main thing is that the information presented in the case has a clear and accessible structure with acceptable and understandable definitions and accurate data. There are a number of works devoted to the use of case studies in a foreign audience, with the concept of which we agree, for example, K. Y. Gayrbekova writes that the purpose of cases in teaching RCT is a way to promote the formation of communicative and socio-cultural knowledge of students learning Russian as a foreign language in the process of creating different communication situations that are extremely close to real ones [2].

Methods I. A. Oskolskaya suggests that when choosing a topic for a training "case", it is worth adhering to the following rules:

1. The specifics of the topic should be simple, that is, the study of the sphere industry should not take more resources than the study of post-established tasks. This experience exceeded all expectations and was soon recognized as promising. And its implementation began at Harvard University also in the teaching of medicine and business administration. In Soviet didactics, the case was introduced into the educational process by S. T. Shatsky. But in the 30s, this method was banned. The case returned to Russian education in the 90s of the twentieth century and became a fairly popular method. As usually happens, the initial idea acquires new meanings, various variants and variations appear, increasingly distancing- esya from the original source. Sometimes it is even difficult to understand why the author of the article writes that he uses a case study: his "cases" are so far from the methodology developed at Harvard. For example, the article by M. A. Shutyak suggests a solution for foreigners studying the Russian language, the solution of which requires one correct answer, which contradicts the idea of an alternative solution to the proposed life situation [3]. I must say that Denmark itself is quite interesting. But what does the case have to do with it? In M. V. Konova's article, for example, we can observe a contradiction in the presentation of the theory case

studies and presented developments. "The model is developed according to certain rules of a specific situation that occurred in real life," the article says [4]. In practice, situations from literary works that have nothing to do with life are offered. We offer a case study in the classical sense, where the case presents a life problem situation that students need to solve based on existing knowledge, practical experience and intuition. Since any situation has several solutions, there are- there will be a discussion of all possible solutions. The use of case studies is limited in the lessons of Russian as a native language, since the features of the material (spelling and punctuation, grammar and phonetics) assume, as a rule, one correct answer when solving a problem situation. But when teaching Russian as a foreign language, the case study can be used quite widely. When solving the problem problem of the case, the ability to listen develops, take into account an alternative point of view and express one's own, orientate and adapt to a new language environment for foreigners, remain-face-to-face with real situations. With this method , quickly adaptable foreign students have the opportunity to be ready to work in a team, to find the most rational solution to the task. Analytical and communicative abilities are formed and developed, research activities are carried out. It is natural to apply situational analysis both for teaching professional and everyday communication. Cases can be offered in various forms: resources from the Internet and periodicals, articles from encyclopedias, announcements, financial and economic reports, letters, materials from archives, and even in the form of audio and video formats. The main thing is that the information presented in the case has a clear and accessible structure with acceptable and understandable definitions and accurate data. There are a number of works devoted to the use of case studies in a foreign audience, with the concept of which we agree, for example, K.Y. Gayrbekova writes that the purpose of cases in teaching RCT is to contribute to the formation of communicative and socio-cultural knowledge of students studying Russian as a foreign language in the process of creating different communication situations, extremely close to the real ones [5]. I. A. Oskolskaya suggests that when choosing a topic for a training "case", it is worth adhering to the following rules:

1. The specifics of the topic should be simple, that is, the study of the sphere industry should not take more resources than the study of the tasks set.
2. The topic must be public, i.e. the required industry data or company statistics are freely available.
3. The topic should be "real", the student should not be distracted by "fiction" in the process of solving [6].

Results In choosing a topic, an individual approach is important and what is relevant for this group of students. It is necessary to focus on the characteristics of

this team: age, country, nationality. Information is selected that is relevant and acceptable for this particular group of students- taking into account national traditions and peculiarities of mentality. For example, we can communicate with students from the USA, Europe on the following topic extramarital relationships, and this conversation is not desirable with Muslim students. It is important to determine the nature of the mutual relations between the participants. How often do they communicate with each other? what emotional climate has formed between the two? We advise you to conduct key studies in groups where the first stage of communication has already been overcome. Otherwise, the distances peculiar to unfamiliar people will not allow individuality to appear openly. And communication will be limited. It must be remembered that the main purpose of the case study method in RCT is communication. There are different methods of conducting the case, for example, according to L. V. Lezhnina, Z. Y. Yuldashev. . In our work, we took the stages of conducting a case on L. V. Lezhnina. This plan is most suitable for conducting discussions between students who have previously communicated. Division into micro-groups in a familiar environment will be perceived by students naturally and will not create problems in discussing a given topic, which will smoothly transfer the conversation from a small circle to a general discussion.

Discussion Stages of the case study by L. V. Lezhnina:

1. Independent acquaintance of the student with the content of the case.
2. Survey on understanding the content of the case.
3. The teacher divides students into micro-groups (4-6 people).
4. Discussion of the content of the case in micro-groups.
5. Presentation of the group's decisions by one of its representatives.
6. Presentation of the solution of the groups as a whole.
7. General discussion and discussion of the received solutions.
8. Generalization of the obtained results and acquired knowledge.

Structure of work in the audience:

1. The teacher's word; problem statement.
2. If necessary, the distribution of students into small groups according to 4-6 people in each).
3. Organization of work in small groups, identification of speakers.
4. Organization of presentation of solutions in small groups.
5. Organization of a general discussion.
6. Generalizing speech of the teacher.
7. Reflection.

When conducting a discussion in an environment unfamiliar to students, where students

communicate with each other for the first time, we recommend the stages of conducting a case on Z. Y. Yuldashev [7].

We have developed ten cases for foreigners. The subject of the cases was chosen not by chance.

REFERENCES:

1. Brown, H. D. (1994). Teaching by principles: An interactive approach to language pedagogy. Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall Regents.
2. Essberger, J. (2012). Speaking versus writing: The pen is mightier than the spoken word or is it?." Weblog entry. 29 May 2012. <http://www.englishclub.com/esl-articles/200108.htm>.
3. Gershon, S. (2010). Developing oral communication skills: What, why and how. Research presenter. Philippine Association for Language Teaching, Inc. (PALT). UP Diliman. 2 December 2010. Lecture.
4. Holly, E. (1999). The focus group research. Illinois, U.S.A. : NTC Business Books.
5. Hyde, S. Identifying intellectually gifted students: Common definitions and characteristics of advanced learners. 9 May 2012. <http://suite101.com/article/identifying-intellectually-gifted-students-a70469>.
6. Juan-Usó, E. & Flor, A.M. (2011). Teaching intercultural communicative competence through the four skills. 21 November 2011.
7. J.J. Jalolov "Chet tillar o'qitish metodikasi" "o'qituvchi" nashriyoti, 2012, p-89